

Impact of Instagram Influencer Marketing on the Restaurant Industry

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ABSTRACT

Communication to the public is a very essential part of any product, service or business. Without adequate communication it is less likely that customers are going to come to you even though you might have a great offering. An offering must be backed by adequate communication in order to let the prospects know that the business or offering exist. A business should consider all the means of communication channels available and use those channels wisely in order to communicate to the public in the most effective way possible. The recent boom in social media platforms has provided a lot of opportunities to marketers and new communication channels, amongst these new communication channels one of the most popular communication channels is Influencer marketing. In this research, the goal is to understand if digital influencers influence the Ahmedabadrestaurant industry positively through dimensions that encompass their characteristics. By using quantitative research methodology, we have formulated a questionnaire and analysed the responses.

1. Introduction

A restaurant has more to offer than just food. Restaurants are not all about people ordering food, finishing and leaving, it's more about how people feel while they are there at the restaurant which could arise from various factors such as the ambience of the restaurant, the theme on which the restaurant is based, the background or even live music. Every restaurant has a specific and distinctive characteristic of their own and hence provides a unique experience to their customers. However, there stands a challenge between the restaurant business and the customers is that how will they attract and create a desire in customers mind so that they would want to know more about it, particularly in light of changing and newer customer demands and expectations. The internet has all kind of information available these days however, customers are now looking for an easy and handy way of getting their hands on information. Influencer marketing has been the most trending marketing technique these days and adopted by several brands to promote themselves. The way it works is that it uses

digital influencers with a vast and huge follower or social base who act as brand ambassadors. These digital influencers with the help of their creativity and content deliver the communication message intended by the brands to their followers by promoting a product on their handle. Influencer marketing is one of the rapid growing sectors of advertising along with that Instagram is also a popular and growing platform. With the help of influencer marketing, restaurants can reach their target audience in an efficient and effective way. This study throws light onto influencer marketing with objectives such as what are the characteristics or factors influencers have that affects the purchase intentions of the audience. Factors such as the expertise of Influencer about restaurants, trustworthiness amongst the audience, Information quality that influencer hold in the shared content they post on Instagram. This way we will find out whether Instagram influencer marketing is really an effective tool and how much impact does it have on the purchase intention of the audience.

1.1 Word of Mouth

Word of mouth is one of the oldest ways for conveying information (Dellarocas, 2003) for marketers as well as consumers. Not only that but it also a very highly credible source of information (Huang & Lan, 2007). Word of mouth sometimes works more effectively than the other tools of communications (Engel et al., 1969). Researches shows that word of mouth has a greater impact than other forms of communication used by marketers s (Mauri and Minazzi, 2013). Every consumer spread a word of mouth about a product or service of brand they have consumed or had some experience with it however, the impact can be positive as well as negative which depends on the kind of experience the customer had with the brand. A satisfied or a delighted customer will always tell his friends or family or social groups about the product or service of brand they consumed whereas a dissatisfied customer will spread negative word of mouth about the same. Word of mouth is so effective that whether it be positive or negative it will have a very significant influence on the decision of the audience. The person receiving word of mouth about a brand from a friend will always look forward to use that particular product of that brand or any product if the word of mouth was spread positively. However, if the same receiver received a negative word of mouth from a trusted friend or family member, it will be always in his mind to avoid that brand because of what his friend recommended about that brand and the person who has had the negative experience will tell around 8 to 16 people about it (Todorov,2022). Word of mouth has a strong impact on consumer behavioural attitudes (Kundu& Rajan, 2017).

According to Nielsen

(2012) 92% of consumers worldwide say they trust recommendations from family and friends more than any other form of advertising. Moreover, according over 83% of consumer are willing to refer it to a friend or family however, only 29% actually do (Turner, 2016). A blog posted by online visibility Management Company SEM Rush (Todorov, 2021) provides more recent word-of-mouth advertising data where it stated various statistics out of which some of them are:

1. 90% people are more likely to trust a brand if recommended even by strangers.
2. Recommendations increased the level of trust in 88% of people when a friend or family member recommended it.
3. Bad word of mouth caused 26% of people to completely avoid a brand and 21% of people lost their trust in a brand.

Word of mouth marketing is still the most effective forms of marketing technique compared to other forms of advertising and around 64% of marketers have the same opinion about it the (Todorov, 2022). However, with the same effectiveness it has now taken a new form which is called e-WOM or electronic word of mouth which is all the marketing information taking place between customers through internet. Word of mouth through electronic means can take place through various modes such as sharing or writing blogs (Thorson and Rodgers, 2006) and reviews (Bickart and Schindler's, 2001), sharing photos and videos on social media platforms to friends or family members, online comments (Pantano and Corvello, 2013). Most marketers are now looking forward to invest more in e-WOM because it increases brand awareness and drives sales as well. So, it's really important for marketers to stay updated, relevant and understand the potential that word of mouth marketing holds with it.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Influencer Marketing

Over the years there has been introduction of many tools for advertising which has changed the advertising mix for marketers. With the introduction to digital media in the marketing mix, there exists a lot of opportunities for marketers to advertise their product or brand on digital platforms such as blogs, reviews, and social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube etc. With the growth of these social media platforms influencer marketing came into picture on social media platforms. Influencer marketing is basically promotion of a brand, product or service by a digital influencer who is a person who has many followers on

social media and is compensated by companies to advertise their products to their audience. This compensation may include free products, trips, or payment for each promotional post. Influential people have the capacity to influence the decision of the audience and drive brand's message to a larger extent. Influencers also help manipulate the purchase intention of audience in appositive way through their content (More &Lingam 2019). Influencer marketing is a very popular form of advertising these days and the market of influencer marketing has grown to \$8 Billion in 2019 from \$1.7 Billion in 2016 and it has now become a whopping \$16.4 Billion industry in 2022 (Sharma, 2021). Instagram has become the prime channel for influencer marketing to reach out to potential customers. The reason behind such popularity and extensive use of this technique is that there is a trust amongst the digital influencer and their followers (Sharma, 2021). Secondly, we can reach to masses or niche as well through digital influencers depending upon the size of follower base an influencer has. A Digital Influencer sharing photos, videos of various lengths showing around the restaurant and the kind of food served while describing about the place in the video or in the description and why one should try it with the paid sponsorship tag is an example of influencer marketing.

(Shepherd, 2023) states that this 44% of B2C brands planned to increase their budget for influencer marketing in 2021 and marketers will continue spending more on influencer marketing. On an average a business will make \$5.20-\$6.5 for every \$1 invested in influencer marketing. 8 out 10 consumers purchased something after seeing a recommendation from an influencer. 60% of marketers stated that influencer generated content performed better than the branded posts and drove more engagement.

Restaurant business is booming with newer restaurants opening up which increases competition for a restaurant to survive. In order to gain a competitive advantage over other restaurants it becomes essential for a business to adopt marketing techniques so that they can not only reach their target audience but also arouse interest and desire in them so that they visit their restaurant. Influencer marketing does just the job for these restaurants. Whenever a new restaurant is launched in the city it is essential that the target audience in every corner of that city knows that this restaurant exists. Raising brand awareness and building brand can easily be done by influencer marketing by inviting influencers to promote your restaurant, in fact even if you have tight budget you can partner with so called micro influencers who has between 10,000-100,000 followers. Micro Influencers are very cost effective for a new restaurant and can help just the right target audience for your business in no time. Micro influencers are on the rise and are growing from 89% to 91% in 2021 (Shepherd, 2023). These influencers promote restaurants in their own creative way with their content which creates authenticity and build high level of trust in the audience's mind.

Influencer marketing has various benefits such as building brand awareness, building high level of loyalty effectively reaching your target audience but while opting for influencer marketing identifying the right kind of influencer which could have the greatest impact on the audience remains a challenge (Dewangan et al., 2022). One cannot just invite any influencer and expect it to have an impact on their business. The possession of a significant number of followers alone does not constitute influence; rather, it is shaped by the influencer's knowledge and trustworthiness in a particular field, as well as the rapport between the influencer and their audience. There are many types of influencers, Mega Influencers (1 Million+ Followers), Macro Influencer (100,000 to 1M Followers), Micro Influencer (10,000 to 100,000 Followers) and Nano Influencers (Fewer than 10,000 Followers) (Hootsuite 2022). A restaurant must carefully select an influencer and they should follow the three Rs of influence while selecting an influencer to promote their brand. The three Rs are Relevance, Reach and Resonance (Hootsuite 2022). The influencer promoting your restaurant must be relevant to this industry and it needs to have audience that aligns with your target audience or this industry. Secondly, number of people you are trying to reach through the influencer and lastly the level of engagement the influencer can create. Keeping these three things in mind with the goals the restaurant should select an influencer and then promote themselves through the influencer.

Hwa, Cheah. (2017), research shows the impact of social media influencers on purchase intention and the mediation effect of customer attitude, it took four factors into consideration which could influence the consumer attitude and ultimately the purchase intention, they were source credibility, source attractiveness, product match up and meaning transfer. The findings revealed that source credibility and source attractiveness had an insignificant relationship and failed to influence consumer attitude and purchase intention, while product matchup and meaning of transfer of social media influencer had a positive and significant impact on consumer attitude and purchase intention.

Jay Trivedi & Ramzan Sama (2020) studied the effect of influencer marketing on consumers' brand admiration and online purchase intentions. The research studied and compared the impact of an expert influencer vis-à-vis an attractive influencer which further had an impact on brand attitude which results in brand admiration and finally leading to purchase intentions. The findings of this research revealed that consumers would listen more to an expert influencer rather than an attractive influencer in case of electronics product. Both expert influencer and attractive influencer had a significant impact on brand attitude which had a greater effect on Brand admiration which led to purchase intention.

Chopra et al., (2020) analyzed various factors that affect consumer behavior through influencer marketing. Factors such as, attitude, source credibility, perceived behavioral control, product influencer fit and subjective norms. The findings revealed that trust emerged as an important trait, personal relevance was also crucial to influence the consumer behavior while perceived risk and subjective norms had a truly little influence.

Anjos et al., (2022) Researched the impact of influencer marketing on specifically restaurants, they studied and analyzed factors such as knowledge on diversity of restaurants, trust, attention and care given to shared content, WOM and paid partnerships. The study revealed that the WOM generated by the influencers had the greatest impact followed by the attention and care influencers take for their content that they shared with the audience and lastly the fact that regular content generates more interest than paid ones but because paid content is credible, creative and transparent it can still have a positive impact on the consumer.

Po-Yen Lee, et.al 2019 Researched about influencer marketing from through data gathered from a restaurant group and the findings stated that before considering influencer marketing a marketing plan must be made for selecting the influencers first. The marketing plan must include setting clear objectives and a reasonable budget for influencer marketing, setting positioning strategies and clarifying the target audience the restaurant wishes to target and determine the various effective influencers.

2.2 Hypotheses

The main objective of this study is to analyze the impact that influencer marketing on the purchase intention of consumers in Ahmedabad. As a result, Purchase Intention can be identified as a dependent variable. On the other hand, the factors that affect purchase intention of consumer in influencer marketing are Expertise of Influencers, their trust, Information Quality of the shared content and likeability as independent variables

H1: The expertise of influencers in the restaurant sector is positively associated with the consumer's purchase intention.

Knowledgeable Influencers have the ability to influence and shape consumer attitude towards a brand in a favorable way and this results in a positive attitude towards the endorsed brand in consumer's mind which leads to purchase intention (Dewangan et al., 2022). Thus, it is hypothesized that expertise of an influencer is positively associated with the consumer's purchase intention.

H2: The trustworthiness of an influencer is positively associated with consumer's purchase intention

Consumers have a favorable attitude towards a brand when they are promoted by an influencer rather than a traditional celebrity, moreover consumers find an endorsement more trustworthy when it's done by an influencer rather than a traditional celebrity (Dewangan et al., 2022). Trust is a critical factor in an influencer that affects the purchase intention of consumer, the more trustworthy the influencer is the more likely a consumer is going to purchase from that endorsement of the influencer. (Chetioui & Lebdaoui, 2020)

H3: The information quality with shared content is positively associated with consumer's purchase intention.

The content shared by the influencer is very crucial while endorsing a brand or product. To attract and maintain the audience, influencers must post content from which consumers derive value which can be either informative or entertainment value, either or both of this has an impact on consumer's purchase intention (Saima & Khan, 2020). In our case the appealing photos and videos of restaurant and food, description of the post explaining the concept of restaurant and the food served here when an influencer visits a restaurant.

H4: Likeability of consumers towards influencers is positively associated to consumer's purchase intention.

Likeability towards influencers has a significant impact on consumer's purchase intention since the followers of influencers develop an emotional attachment with the influencer and will strongly follow their recommendations if they feel associated with the influencer because the followers are somehow able to relate themselves to the influencer (Dewangan et al., 2022). Thus, it is hypothesized that likeability is positively associated towards consumer's purchase intention.

Based on the above hypothesis, following conceptual model is being proposed. (Figure 1)

Figure 1- Hypothesised Model (developed by author)

3. Methodology

3.1 Sample

The study was carried out using a descriptive research design by the researchers and followed a non-probability sampling method. The respondents were given an online structured questionnaire which was administered through various social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp. There was a filter question to identify the appropriate respondents. The question required the respondent to fill the questionnaire only if they followed influencers on social media platforms. There was another filter question on whether they have gone to a restaurant which was endorsed by any influencer. This question enabled the researchers to target the appropriate audience, as the participants were then directed to the subsequent section of the questionnaire, which consisted of statements pertaining to the factors that were considered in the study. The data was obtained from 250 respondents who were users of various social media platforms. Out of these, only 150 respondents were following a social media influencer and only 129 had gone to a restaurant promoted by an influencer. So only those 129 responses were considered for further data analysis.

3.2 Measurement

The constructs used in the study were taken from previous literature, with some modifications based on the qualitative judgement of the researchers. The initial version of the questionnaire was pre-tested with 20 people to get the feedback and check the reliability of the survey instrument. This led to reformulation of ambiguous questions and elimination of irrelevant ones. All the required changes were made and the final version of the questionnaire was made. The survey instrument was divided into three sections- first section had general questions on social media usage and restaurant going behaviour. The second section followed with questions related to expertise, trustworthiness, information quality, likability of the influencer and purchase intentions. To assess the various constructs in the research, participants were asked to rate each statement on a scale of one to five, where one represented "strongly disagree" and five represented "strongly agree". The third section included demographic determinants such as- age, gender, area, education and occupation.

4. Data Analysis

4.1 Respondents Profile

The demographic profile of the respondents is given in the table 1 below. There is a balanced representation of gender in the sample as 55.8 % are females and 44.2 % are males. About 76.74 % of the respondents eat at a restaurant more than 2 times in a month. There are 90.7 % of the respondents in the age group of 18-25, as this age group is the most dominant user of social media.

Table 1: Respondents Demographic Profile

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	144	55.8
	Male	114	44.2
Age	18-25	200	77.52
	26-30	53	20.5
	31-40	5	1.9
Education	High School	17	6.5
	Bachelor	80	31
	Masters	108	41.86
	Post-Graduation	53	20.54
Occupation	Salaried	82	31.78
	Self Employed	9	3.5
	Student	167	64.73

4.2 Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's coefficient alpha was used to assess the internal consistency of scales. A value of 0.7 or higher is considered reliable, according to Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994. In this study, the internal consistency of all constructs was satisfactory, with all values exceeding 0.7. The item to total statistics in case of variable likability, improved with deletion of a particular item. Therefore, that item was removed to improve the reliability of the scale. The final number of scale items of each variable with its Cronbach alpha is given in the Table 2 below:

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

Variable	No of Items	Cronbach Alpha
Expertise	5	0.765
Trustworthiness	3	0.705
Likability	4	0.741
Information	4	0.82
Quality		
Purchase Intention	3	0.723

In the social sciences, composite scores are frequently utilized to represent variables or concepts that cannot be directly measured by a single data point. A composite score is a value that amalgamates information from multiple variables or data points into a single measure or score. To create a composite score, it is common to either sum all of the ratings together or take the average (mean) of the ratings from the multiple data points. However, a composite score should only be made from sets of items that are strongly related. In our study the Cronbach alpha of all variables were high and statistically significant. Considering the goals of our research, an analysis based on composite score will provide a clearer answer than a separate analysis for each of the items. Additionally, having fewer variables to analyze can lead to a decrease in the number of statistical analyses that need to be conducted, thereby reducing the likelihood of making Type I errors. So, for further analysis a composite score for each of the variables was used.

The next step in the analysis was examining the dimensionality of the developed scale. This was accomplished by performing Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) of the difference score. Two statistical measures are used to assess the factorability of the data: Bartlett's test of sphericity (Bartlett, 1954) and the Kaiser- Meyer- Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy (Kaiser 1970, 1974). Bartlett's test of sphericity should be significant ($p < 0.05$) for the factor analysis to be considered appropriate. The KMO index ranges from 0 to 1 with 0.60 suggested as the minimum value for a good factor analysis (Tabachnick & Fidell 2007). As per Table 2, the Bartlett test of sphericity is significant with a p value of 0.000 and the KMO measure of sampling adequacy is 0.928, which far greater than the minimum value of 0.6 (Tabachnick & Fidell 2007).

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.641
Approx. Chi-Square		4336.558
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	210
	Sig.	.000

Exploratory Factor Analysis was conducted using Principal component Analysis (PCA) as the extraction method. The decision to include a variable in a factor was based on factor loadings greater than ± 0.3 (Hair et al. 1995), and all factors whose Eigen values was greater than 1.0 were retained in the factor solution (Tabachnick & Fidell 1989). The choice regarding factor loadings greater than ± 0.3 was not based on any mathematical proposition but relates more to practical significance. The results from EFA showed a formation of 4 factors of Influencer characteristics. The results of the factor analysis is given below

Table 3 Results of factor analysis of difference score of service quality (Extraction method: principal Axis Factoring (PAF); Rotation Method: Direct OBLIMIN)

Factor	Items	Eigen Values	% Variance	Factor Loading	Reliability
Understanding the Customer	U3	14.124	36.934	0.416	0.783
	U1			0.366	
	U4			0.329	
	U5			0.329	
Assurance	A1	2.206	41.731	0.74	0.882
	A2			0.736	
	A3			0.734	
	A4			0.717	
	A5			0.632	
	A6			0.626	
Image	I1	1.727	45.097	0.72	0.751
	I2			0.531	
	I3			0.467	
	I4			0.377	
Employee Approach	E1	1.445	47.717	0.582	0.864
	E2			0.475	
	E3			0.446	
	E4			0.411	
	E5			0.406	
Tangibles	T1	1.286	49.88	0.633	0.767

	T2			0.436	
	T3			0.408	
	T4			0.381	
	T5			0.349	
Access	A1	1.063	51.562	0.825	0.809
	A2			0.626	
	A3			0.409	
	A4			0.391	
Communication	C1	1.021	53.037	0.652	0.68
	C2			0.369	
	C3			0.348	

However, through observation of the solution showed that the factors which were different from the original 10 dimensions, included items conceptually sharing a common core value. As a final step Cronbach’s alpha coefficient is determined, to measure internal consistency so as to ensure that the items comprising the factors produce a reliable scale. The alpha values are summarized along with Eigen values, Variance and Factor loadings in the table 3. In the final run of the factor analysis for service quality, 34 items were found to define the seven dimensions of perceived service quality. The seven-factor solution explained a total of 53% of variance, which is higher than 50 % as recommended by Nunnally & Bernstein (1994). Communalities of the 34 items ranged from 0.335 to 0.709, which were above the acceptable level of 0.30.

4.3. Correlation Analysis

A correlation analysis was conducted to study the degree of association between various variables. The purpose was to determine the correlation between expertise, trustworthiness, likability, information quality and the purchase intention of consumers. The correlation coefficients are shown in the below Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

	Purchase Intention	Expertise	Trustworthiness	Likability	Information Quality
Purchase Intention	1				
Expertise	0.754	1			
Trustworthiness	0.727	0.627	1		
Likability	0.827	0.692	0.604	1	
Information	0.812	0.799	0.683	0.662	1

All the correlations are positive and significant at $\alpha=0.01$ level. The composite score of multiple items was considered for the analysis of each construct. The strongest correlation was observed between likability and purchase intention ($r=0.827, p<0.01$), which was followed by Information quality and purchase intention ($r=0.812, p<0.01$).

4.4 Multiple Regression Analysis

To determine the impact of various variables related to influencers on purchase intentions in restaurant industry, linear regression was conducted. The r^2 value in the model provides a measure of the predictive ability of the model. The closer the value r^2 equals 1, the better the regression model fits the data. The r^2 value of the regression model was 0.82 and the overall model was statistically significant at 0.01 level (Table 4). The variables- expertise, trustworthiness, likability and information quality together explained 82% of purchase intentions of consumers.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	148.774	4	37.193	146.531	0
Residual	31.475	124	0.254		
Total	180.248	128			

As demonstrated in the below table, all the variables have an impact on the purchase intention of the consumers. Hypothesis H1 on expertise ($\beta = .0.243, p < 0.01$), H2 on trustworthiness ($\beta = 0.596, p < 0.01$), H3 on likability ($\beta = 0.209, p < 0.01$), and H4 on information quality ($\beta = 0.194, p < 0.01$) was found to be statistically significant.

Table 5: Regression results

Sr.no	Hypothesis	Coefficient	Std Error	t value	p Value	Conclusion
H1	Expertise → Purchase Intention	0.243	0.089	2.727	0.007	Significant
H2	Trustworthiness → Purchase Intention	0.596	0.069	8.571	0	Significant
H3	Likability → Purchase Intention	0.209	0.07	2.973	0.004	Significant
H4	Information Quality → Purchase Intention	0.194	0.059	3.276	0.001	Significant

5. Discussion

The aim of this research was to study the impact of these factors, expertise, trustworthiness, likeability and information quality on purchase intention of a consumer for restaurants. The ultimate objective was to check whether the consumers go to a restaurant after they see an influencer endorsing it or not and how do these factors affect it. After analysing the responses, we found out that trustworthiness had the most significant impact on consumer’s purchase intention which is similar to the findings of (Chopra et.al 2020) where trust emerged as an essential trait. We found out that to influence the consumers it is important that the influencer itself, their content and their information must be credible which will greatly impact the purchase decision of a consumer. Influencer marketing or endorsement works similar to word of mouth where people would trust the recommendations of friends or family more. Similarly, people would trust an influencer more rather than a traditional advertisement by a celebrity. The next factor, expertise had a significant impact on purchase intention of consumer. It is important that the influencer has knowledge about the product they are endorsing, in our case restaurants. Influencers need to be aware of the kind of restaurants they are endorsing, the similarities and differences between different restaurants, influencers should be able to identify and fulfil their audience’s needs through their expertise about restaurants. Influencer can only fulfil audience needs such as looking for different options of restaurants and wanting to understand about the restaurant’s concept if influencer has great pool of knowledge about various different restaurants. Expertise of the influencer will result in more credibility and thus impact the purchase intention for a consumer. These findings were similar to that of (Chetioui and Lebdaoui, 2020). Expertise was followed by Likeability which had a significant impact on purchase intention of consumer. Likeability is when consumers like a particular influencer which could be because of various reason, their content, personality or something with which the consumers are able to relate

themselves which results in consumers developing an emotional attachment with the influencer which leads to positive image of the influencer and the brands that are endorsing themselves through that influencer (Dewangan et al., 2022). Likeability not only helps in attracting the audience but maintaining a sustainable and long-term relationship with them. Lastly comes the factor of information quality which had the least impact on purchase intention of consumer. Information quality can be referred as the information value and entertainment value consumers derive from the content shared by the influencer. The better the information is or value consumers derive from it the more credible and trustworthy an influencer is perceived, it regards to how much attention do the influencers pay to their content quality and description, the content must be informative as well as entertaining like appealing photos or videos of the restaurant, food and the ambience helps attract audience and stimulate an impulse in them towards the influencer as well as the restaurant.

6. Theoretical Contributions

The research was focused on assessing the factors or characteristics of influencer marketing that influence the purchase intention of a consumer. The factors were analysed individually and in depth rather than grouping few factors into one as done in previous researches (Hwa, 2017; Niloy et al.2023) Rather than grouping expertise and trustworthiness into one group as source credibility we kept them separate to analyse the impact of each factor on purchase intention. Likeability and Information Quality were other two factors which were taken into consideration for analysing their impact on purchase intention of consumer. Again, likeability was taken into consideration rather than source attractiveness as done in previous researches because source attractiveness had an insignificant impact towards influencing the consumer but a positive or a favourable towards the influencer has a rather great impact on consumer. Information Quality is the quality of the content the influencer shares with their audience, it is important that the message or content shared must fit with the audience otherwise it can have a negative impact on the consumer which was analysed in the research where it had a positive impact on consumer's purchase intention unlike previous researches. (Saima & Khan, 2020).

7. Practical Implications

Brand managers, marketers who are looking forward to use influencer marketing as their communication or promotional tool in their strategy can assure that their investment won't go into vain by taking into account these factors, Trustworthiness, Expertise, Likeability and Information Quality. Marketers can consider these effects for selecting the right influencer who fulfils their objectives in the best way possible. Trustworthiness had the most impact on purchase intention hence marketers must look out for influencers who are perceived

trustworthy by their audience, marketers can also identify influencers with rest of the factors in such a way which results in high level of trustworthiness such as an influencer with expertise in the restaurant field will be perceived credible which can be identified through the content and the description of their posts, which also sums up Information Quality. However, the audience should also be able to emotionally connect with the influencer which will result in favourable image of influencer as well as restaurant in consumer's mind. Taking into account the above factors while also considering some digital marketing factors such as formulating a proper digital marketing strategy and considering the three R's of selecting an influencer as well, marketers can get the most returns or benefits out of influencer marketing.

8. Scope for future research

In this research Information Quality had the least effect on purchase intention however positive. Further studies can deeply examine the type of content, content strategies and how much impact do they have on consumers. Also, future researches can study the impact of influencers on purchase intention who were content creators before and later on started endorsing products for few brands and influencers who solely do influencer marketing from the very beginning for various brands. Future researches can also use qualitative methods to examine the impact of the factors even more closely or identify any such other factors that might influence consumer's purchase intention, Qualitative methods can also be used to gain insights from successful influencer to understand their strategy for successful influencer marketing campaign.

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